

1 **Strong correlation of oxygen vacancy in bridgmanite with Mg/Si ratios**

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8 **Abstract**

9 The variation of an oxygen vacancy (OV) in the form of an MgAlO_{2.5} component in
10 bridgmanite with Mg/Si ratios of bulk compositions was clarified in phase relations in the
11 ternary system MgO–AlO_{1.5}–SiO₂ at a pressure of 27 GPa and a temperature of 2000 K using
12 advanced multi-anvil techniques. Both normal and reversed experiments suggest that
13 significant amounts of the OV component exists in bridgmanite synthesized from the bulk
14 composition with the Mg/Si ratio above unity. The OV component significantly decreases with
15 decreasing Mg/Si ratio, and it finally becomes negligible for the Mg/Si ratio below unity. In
16 contrast, the charge-coupled (CC) component of AlAlO₃ becomes more dominant. The ternary
17 phase relations further indicate that bridgmanite in a pyrolitic or peridotitic lower mantle will
18 contain certain amounts of OV component, while that in mid-ocean ridge basalts (MORB) will
19 not contain any amount of this component. Our study suggests that significant amounts of
20 volatiles such as argon trapped by the OV of bridgmanite may be induced into the ambient
21 lower mantle, while they cannot be brought into basaltic slabs by bridgmanite but other phases
22 such as hydrous phases. The decrease of the OV in bridgmanite with decreasing Mg/Si ratio
23 may offer a simple explanation for some stagnant slabs in the lower mantle.

24 **Key words:** Oxygen vacancy, Mg/Si ratio, bridgmanite, volatile, slab stagnation, lower mantle

25 1. Introduction

26 Bridgmanite, the most abundant phase in the lower mantle (about 80% by volume), can
27 contain significant amounts of aluminum (Al) (Irifune, 1994; Tschauner *et al.*, 2014). Al
28 substitution in bridgmanite can occur in the forms of AlAlO_3 and $\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}$. These two
29 components, referred to as the CC (charge-couple) component and OV (oxygen-vacancy)
30 component, respectively, affect differently the chemistry and elastic properties of bridgmanite.
31 The OV component appears to considerably decrease the bulk modulus of bridgmanite
32 (Zhang and Weidner, 1999; Brodholt, 2000; Daniel *et al.* 2001; Andrault *et al.*, 2007) and it
33 may transport water (Navrotsky, 1999; Murakami *et al.*, 2002) and noble gases (Shcheka and
34 Keppler, 2012) into the lower mantle (Liu *et al.*, 2017a). In contrast, the CC component does
35 not affect the bulk modulus significantly (Walter *et al.*, 2004, 2006; Yagi *et al.*, 2004), and it
36 cannot incorporate volatiles into the bridgmanite structure. Hence, it is important to investigate
37 the conditions for which each Al substitution mechanism dominates in order to understand the
38 structure and geochemical circulation in the lower mantle.

39 In a pyrolitic mantle composition with an Mg/Si ratio of 1.3, bridgmanite coexists with
40 ferropericlase (MgO) (Irifune, 1994), whereas it coexists with stishovite (SiO_2) for the
41 composition of mid-ocean ridge basalts (MORB) with a very low Mg/Si ratio of 0.5 (Hirose *et al.*
42 *et al.*, 2005). It is expected that the OV component will dominate in bridgmanite for MgO-rich
43 conditions rather than for SiO_2 -rich conditions (Navrotsky, 1999; Walter *et al.*, 2006; Andrault
44 *et al.*, 2007). Navrotsky *et al.* (2003), Kojitani *et al.* (2007a) and Liu *et al.* (2017a) indeed
45 showed that the OV component was prevalent in the system MgSiO_3 – $\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}$ that
46 corresponded to MgO-rich conditions, at pressures corresponding to the uppermost part of the
47 lower mantle. Petrological studies on the system MgSiO_3 – Al_2O_3 (Irifune *et al.*, 1996; Kubo
48 and Akaogi, 2000; Liu *et al.*, 2016, 2017b), which provided more Si-rich conditions, suggested
49 that the CC component becomes dominant in the deeper lower mantle, while the OV

50 component becomes negligible. Furthermore, [Walter et al. \(2006\)](#) studied phase relations in
51 $\text{MgSiO}_3\text{--MgAlO}_{2.5}$, $\text{MgSiO}_3\text{--MgAl}_2\text{O}_4$, and $\text{MgSiO}_3\text{--Al}_2\text{O}_3$ systems using a laser-heated
52 diamond anvil cell (LHDAC) combined with *in-situ* X-ray diffraction, suggesting that the OV
53 component plays a negligible role even in MgO-rich systems in the lower mantle. Thus, it is
54 still unclear what effect the bulk composition has on the substitution mechanism of Al in
55 bridgmanite.

56 In this study, we systematically investigated the content of the OV and CC component in
57 bridgmanite with varying Mg/Si ratios for the bulk compositions in ternary system
58 $\text{MgO--AlO}_{1.5}\text{--SiO}_2$ using a multi-anvil press with tungsten carbide anvils. The pressure and
59 temperature condition in this study were 27 GPa and 2000 K in order to avoid the presence of
60 majorite, which may have cause additional complication in the phase relations. With these
61 experiments, we could constrain the OV content in bridgmanite in the uppermost part of the
62 lower mantle, and then discuss its implications for the mineralogy, dynamics, and geochemical
63 cycling in the lower mantle.

64 **2. Materials and Methods**

65 We prepared eight different starting compositions, which are shown in **Fig. 1**. The starting
66 materials A, C, E, and G are glasses with compositions of $\text{En}_{90}\text{Brm}_{10}$ (Brm: $\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}$
67 brownmillerite), $\text{En}_{95}\text{Sp}_5$ (Sp: MgAl_2O_4 spinel), $\text{En}_{95}\text{Cor}_5$ (Cor: Al_2O_3 corundum), and $\text{En}_{95}\text{Ky}_5$
68 (Ky: Al_2SiO_5 kyanite), while B, D, F, and H are fine-grained oxide mixtures of $\text{En}_{52}\text{Brm}_{48}$,
69 $\text{En}_{50}\text{Sp}_{50}$, $\text{En}_{50}\text{Cor}_{50}$, and $\text{En}_{50}\text{Ky}_{50}$. Their general features are as follows. The compositions of
70 A (Mg/Si = 1.06) and B (Mg/Si = 1.75) mixtures are on the tie line of MgSiO_3 to $\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}$.
71 The C (Mg/Si = 1.02) and D (Mg/Si = 1.76) mixtures are on the tie line of MgSiO_3 to MgAl_2O_4 ,
72 those of mixtures E (Mg/Si = 1.00) and F (Mg/Si = 0.99) are on the tie line of MgSiO_3 to Al_2O_3 .
73 Finally, the G (Mg/Si = 0.92) and H (Mg/Si = 0.48) mixtures are on the tie line of MgSiO_3 to
74 Al_2SiO_5 . The glasses were prepared from oxide mixtures of reagent-grade MgO, SiO_2 , and

75 Al₂O₃, which were fused at a temperature of 2000 K for 1 hour, quenched into cold water and
76 ground into fine-grained powder. This process was repeated three times in order to obtain
77 homogeneous glass starting material. The fine-grained oxide mixtures were prepared from
78 reagent-grade oxide chemicals with very small grain sizes of ~100 nm in order to enhance
79 reactions at 27 GPa and 2000 K (Liu *et al.*, 2016, 2017b). The compositions of these starting
80 materials were measured with an electron probe microanalyze (See Supplementary Table S1).
81 The starting materials were put into platinum capsules, and heated at 800 K for 1 hour before
82 being used in the high-pressure cell assembly in order to minimize the amount of adhesive
83 water.

84 Synthesis experiments at 27 GPa and 2000 K were performed using a Cr₂O₃-doped MgO
85 octahedra with 7-mm edge length and a LaCrO₃ sleeve for heating in combination with
86 tungsten carbide cubes with 3-mm truncated edge lengths in a Kawai-type multi-anvil
87 apparatus with a press load of 15 MN at the Bayerisches Geoinstitut, University of Bayreuth
88 (IRIS-15) (Ishii *et al.*, 2016). Pressure calibrations at 2000 K were calibrated based on the
89 solubility of Al₂O₃ in bridgmanite coexisting with corundum (Liu *et al.*, 2017b). The pressure
90 uncertainties of these experiments are ± 0.5 GPa.

91 Textural observations and chemical analyses of the recovered samples were performed
92 using an LEO1530 scanning electron microscope (SEM) and a JEOL JXA-8200 electron probe
93 microanalyzer (EPMA) operating at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV and a beam current of 5
94 nA with enstatite and forsterite for Mg and Si standards, respectively, and corundum for Al.
95 We measured the composition of pure MgSiO₃ bridgmanite (Liu *et al.*, 2016) using the same
96 setting as a benchmark analysis. The phases present were identified using a micro-focused
97 X-ray diffractometer (MF-XRD), a Bruker D8 DISCOVER equipped with a two-dimensional
98 solid state detector (VANTEC500), and a micro-focus source (I μ S) with Co-K α radiation
99 operated at 40 kV and 500 μ A. The X-ray beam was focused to 50 μ m using an IFG
100 polycapillary X-ray mini-lens. XRD profiles of each sample were collected for two hours. The

101 Bragg angles (2θ) of the MF-XRF were calibrated using MgSiO_3 bridgmanite as an external
102 standard.

103 **3. Results**

104 **3.1 Phase assemblages**

105 Experimental conditions and phases present in the recovered samples are summarized in
106 **Table 1**. The starting materials with compositions near pure- MgSiO_3 (A, C, and E) produce a
107 single-phase of bridgmanite except for the SiO_2 -rich system (G), which crystallizes to a
108 bridgmanite + stishovite assemblage from XRD and SEM observations (**Fig. 2** and **3**). The
109 run products from starting materials with a larger secondary components (B, D, F, and H)
110 consist of bridgmanite plus one or two additional phases (**Fig. 2** and **3**). The coexisting
111 phases change from periclase + CF phase (B) to CF phase+ corundum (D) to corundum (F)
112 and finally to corundum + stishovite (G).

113 **3.2 Composition**

114 Compositions of bridgmanite in the recovered samples are shown in **Table 2**, and those of
115 additional phases coexisted with bridgmanite are shown in Supplementary Table S2.
116 Bridgmanite for A, C, E, and G contains almost the same Al_2O_3 content (5 wt.%), which is
117 also comparable with that of their glass starting material. The Mg/Si ratio of these
118 synthesized bridgmanite is almost close to that of the bulk starting materials within analytical
119 uncertainties except G. The Mg/Si ratio of bridgmanite from G is 0.99, which is significantly
120 higher than that of the starting material (0.92) due to the existence of some amount of minor
121 stishovite in this sample. The Al_2O_3 content in bridgmanite increases from 8.1 wt.% for B to
122 10.5 wt.% for D and to 12.6 wt.% for F and then decrease to 10.9 wt.% for H. It's found that
123 the appearing CF phase in B and D contains significant amounts of the Mg_2SiO_4 component,
124 and this component would decrease from 34 mol% from B to 30 mol% for D. The corundum

125 in samples D, F, and H contains 19, 21, and 20 mol% MgSiO₃ component, respectively. The
126 periclase and stishovite in B and H, respectively, also contain small amounts of Al₂O₃
127 component of 0.3 and 2.0 mol%. We also did one reversed experiment in the run IRIS478 for
128 the powder sample of the run products of B and D, which were synthesized at 27 GPa and 2000
129 K for 22-26 hours in the runs IRIS427 and IRIS446, for additional 20-26 hours at the same
130 pressure and temperature. Bridgmanite from B and D in this reversed run contains about 8.3
131 and 10.9 wt.% Al₂O₃, respectively, which are comparable to those (8.1 and 10.5 wt.%) for B
132 and D in the synthesized runs IRIS427 and IRIS446,. The CF phase, corundum, and periclase
133 also show nearly consistent compositions with those in the above synthesis runs within
134 analytical uncertainties. This fact suggests that chemical equilibrium was achieved for
135 experiments at 27 GPa and 2000 K for keeping 22-26 hours in our experiments.

136 The content of the OV (MgAlO_{2.5}) and CC (AlAlO₃) components in bridgmanite were
137 derived from the reaction of $Mg_xAl_zSi_yO_{x+1.5z+2y} = y MgSiO_3 + (x-y) MgAlO_{2.5} + (z-x+y)/2$
138 $AlAlO_3$ ($x + y + z = 2$, [Liu et al. 2017a](#)). **Fig. 4a** shows the variation of the OV and CC content
139 in the synthesized bridgmanite with Al pfu (pfu: per formula units) of 0.1 as a function of the
140 Mg/Si ratio. It was noted that the OV content in bridgmanite rapidly decreases from 4.9 mol%
141 to approximately zero with the Mg/Si ratio decreasing from 1.05 for bridgmanite synthesized
142 from A to 1.00 for that from G. In contrast, the corresponding CC content increases from 2.6 to
143 5.6 mol%. This fact suggests that both OV and CC mechanisms take place in the MgO-rich
144 systems, with OV being dominant with respect to CC. However, with increasing Si content
145 from A to G, the excess Si relative to Mg in the starting compositions favors the substitution of
146 Al to form the CC component rather than the OV component. In addition, the OV and CC
147 components suppress each other because the Al content in bridgmanite is nearly constant with
148 the changing Mg/Si ratio from A to G.

149 For bridgmanites with Al pfu above 0.1 that coexisted with one or two additional
150 phases in B, D, F, and H, the OV gradually decreases from 2.0 mol% to nearly zero with a

151 decreasing Mg/Si ratio from 1.02 to 1.00 for these synthesized bridgmanite (**Fig. 4b**). On the
152 contrary, the CC content significantly increases with decreasing Mg/Si ratio in these
153 bridgmanites. However, the slope of the dependence of the OV decreasing versus Mg/Si ratios
154 for Al-rich bridgmanite is slightly lower than that for bridgmanite with Al pfu of 0.1,
155 suggesting that the high Al might disfavor OV in Al-rich bridgmanite. These results can be
156 explained by the decomposition of the $\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}$ and MgAl_2O_4 component in the latter
157 discussion.

158 **3.3 Molar volume**

159 The unit-cell lattice parameters of all phases present in the recovered samples are shown in
160 Supplementary Table S3, and the molar volume of bridgmanite with Al pfu of 0.1 is plotted
161 versus the Mg/Si ratio of the synthesized bridgmanite from different starting materials in **Fig.**
162 **5a**. In general, the molar volume of bridgmanite decreases with decreasing Mg/Si ratios. In
163 more detail, the molar volume ($24.59 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$) of bridgmanite synthesized in the En-Brm
164 system, namely Mg-rich systems is significantly higher than those ($24.50 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$) of
165 bridgmanite crystallized in the more Si-rich systems such as En-Cor and En-Ky systems. In
166 **Fig. 5b**, a linear function was used to fit the data for CC-bearing bridgmanite synthesized
167 from the En-Cor and En-Ky systems by fixing the endmember of MgSiO_3 bridgmanite. The
168 following equation was obtained: $V(X) = 24.44 + 0.0135(5) \cdot X_{\text{AlAlO}_3}$ ($0 < X_{\text{AlAlO}_3} \leq 15$),
169 where V is the molar volume, X_{AlAlO_3} is the mole content of AlAlO_3 in bridgmanite, and the
170 number in parentheses represents the standard deviation for the last digits. After that, we
171 fitted the pure OV-bearing bridgmanite by subtracting the effect of the CC component and got
172 $V(X) = 24.44 + 0.023(2) \cdot X_{\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}}$ ($0 < X_{\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}} < 6$), where $X_{\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}}$ is the mole content of
173 $\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}$ in bridgmanite. This fact suggests that 1 mol% OV would increase by 2 times
174 higher for molar volume than the same content of CC component.

175 **4. Discussions**

176 **4.1 Al substitution reactions in bridgmanite in the ternary system MgO–AlO_{1.5}–SiO₂**

177 The compositions of bridgmanite, CF phase, periclase, corundum, and stishovite
178 obtained in the present study are summarized in the phase diagram in the ternary system MgO–
179 AlO_{1.5}–SiO₂ (**Fig. 6a**). In the En-Brm system, the majority of the Brm component in the
180 starting material A (En₉₀Brm₁₀) forms the OV component in bridgmanite, which can be
181 explained by the following equation:

183 Since a small amount of the CC component is also contained in this bridgmanite, the following
184 reaction should have occurred:

186 The starting material B (En₅₂Brm₄₈) produced periclase and a calcium-ferrite type
187 (Mg,Al,Si)₃O₄ (CF) in addition to bridgmanite (**Fig. 2 and 3**), which can be explained by the
188 following reaction:

190 Both equation (2) and (3) suggest that end-member MgAlO_{2.5} bridgmanite cannot exist in the
191 lower mantle, and it will decompose into the CF phase or corundum and periclase. Thus, the
192 OV component in bridgmanite would decrease in Al-rich bridgmanite in this system (**Fig. 4b**).

193 In the En-Sp system, the starting material C (En₉₅Sp₅) crystallized into a single phase of
194 bridgmanite, indicating that this amount of MgAl₂O₄ component could completely dissolve
195 into bridgmanite. Since the component of MgAl₂O₄ is intermediate between OV and CC, the
196 reaction can be expressed by:

198 This kind bridgmanite thus contains both OV and CC components. For the D starting material
199 (En₅₀Sp₅₀), bridgmanite coexisted with the CF phase and corundum (**Fig. 2** and **3**), which can
200 be explained by the following reaction:

202 It would thus result a wide solid solution for the CF phase between the endmembers of
203 MgAl₂O₄ and Mg₂SiO₄.

204 For the case of the En-Cor system, the starting material E (En₉₅Cor₅) crystallized into
205 a single phase of bridgmanite, whereas F (En₅₀Cor₅₀) gave rise to bridgmanite with 11.7 mol%
206 corundum, which is in agreement with previous studies ([Irifune et al., 1996](#); [Kubo and Akaogi,](#)
207 [2000](#); [Liu et al. 2016, 2017b](#)). In the En-Ky system, the starting materials G (En₉₅Ky₅) and H
208 (En₅₀Ky₅₀) crystallized to bridgmanite plus stishovite both without and with corundum (**Fig.2**
209 and **3**), respectively.

210 Noted that a single-phase region of bridgmanite was formed towards the MgO-rich
211 region in the ternary phase relations (**Fig. 6a**). From the magnified ternary phase diagram in
212 **Fig. 6b**, it can be seen that the compositions of bridgmanite with a low Al content (Al pfu of
213 0.1) synthesized in the En-Brm system (Mg/Si > 1) are close to the ideal line of a complete
214 oxygen vacancy substitution (OVS), while those obtained in the En-Cor and En-Ky systems
215 (Mg/Si ≤ 1) lie on the line of the charge-coupled substitution (CCS). This fact further
216 supports the result obtained in **Fig.4a** which demonstrates the excess MgO favors the OV
217 component in bridgmanite, while the excess SiO₂ minimizes this component and favors the CC
218 component.

219 Although [Navrotsky et al. \(2003\)](#) attempted to characterize the relations of the OV and
220 CC content with bulk composition, they were not able to find any clear correlation. One
221 possible reason is that in the mentioned study, the LH-DAC was the technique used for the
222 majority of the high-pressure-temperature bridgmanite synthesis. However, to constrain the
223 effect of the bulk composition on the Al substitution mechanism in bridgmanite, very

224 reproducible pressure and temperature conditions, as well as high-quality chemical analysis by
225 means of EPMA are required. These are very difficult conditions to obtain in LH-DAC
226 experiments, though. Another reason may be that the majority of bridgmanite synthesized by
227 means of multi-anvil runs in the mentioned study of [Navrotsky et al. \(2003\)](#) did not coexist
228 with any excess phase and only a few of them coexisted with only one phase. Since the present
229 chemical system consists of three components, *i.e.* MgO, Al₂O₃, and SiO₂, two excess phases
230 are necessary to fix the composition of bridgmanite. In our study, we conducted experiments
231 both with and without excess phases for four different secondary components. This strategy
232 allowed us to constrain the OV and CC contents as a function of the Mg/Si ratio.

233 Our result may explain the large variation of the bulk moduli found in aluminous
234 bridgmanite from various starting materials and different Mg/Si ratios by [Andrault et al.](#)
235 [\(2007\)](#). They found that bridgmanite from MgO-excess starting material possesses a relatively
236 lower bulk modulus (243 GPa) than that from SiO₂-excess starting material (272 GPa) under
237 almost the same pressure range. This can be understood from the fact that OV-bearing
238 bridgmniate becomes more compressible due to a higher molar volume of the OV component
239 than the CC component (**Fig.5**).

240 **4.2 Implications for geochemical circulation**

241 Here, we investigated which Al substitution mechanism dominates in the lower-mantle
242 rocks. We simplified the bulk composition of pyrolite and MORB by assuming that Fe²⁺, Ca²⁺
243 and Mn²⁺ behave in the same way as Mg²⁺, denoted as X²⁺ hereafter, and that Fe³⁺ and Cr³⁺
244 behave in the same way as Al³⁺, denoted as Y³⁺. There are some debates about the Fe³⁺ fraction
245 of the total iron (Fe³⁺/ΣFe) in the lower mantle ([Frost and McCammon, 2008](#)) and the Fe³⁺ sites
246 in bridgmanite depending on the trivalent cation content and pressure ([Frost and Langenhorst,](#)
247 [2002](#); [Fujino et al., 2012](#)). We considered two extreme cases. The first case (case 1) is that
248 Fe³⁺/ΣFe in the lower mantle is identical to that (3 %) in the upper mantle ([Frost and](#)
249 [McCammon, 2008](#)). The second case (case 2) is that the Fe³⁺/ΣFe ratio of bridgmanite in

250 equilibrium with metallic Fe is more than 50% for a typical mantle Al₂O₃ content (*e.g.*,
251 [McCammon, 1997](#); [Frost *et al.*, 2004](#); [Frost and McCammon, 2008](#)) and Fe³⁺ prefers Mg sites
252 due to the similar cation size in the uppermost lower mantle ([Fujino *et al.*, 2012](#)). In the case 1,
253 the bulk X:Y:Si ratios of pyrolite and MORB are 0.57:0.05:0.38 and 0.34:0.18:0.48,
254 respectively. In the case 2, the bulk X:Y:Si ratios of pyrolite and MORB are 0.54:0.08:0.38 and
255 0.31:0.21:0.48, respectively. As shown in **Fig. 7**, the pyrolite compositions for the case 1 and 2
256 are located in the region of bridgmanite + periclase and that of bridgmanite + CF phase +
257 periclase, respectively. Therefore, the OV component will be the major component of Al
258 incorporation. We estimated that the bridgmanite from the pyrolite bulk composition will
259 contain 9 and 4 mol% of the OV (XYO_{2.5}) components in the case 1 and 2, respectively. In
260 contrast, the bulk compositions of the MORB for both case 1 and 2 are located in the region of
261 bridgmanite + stishovite + corundum, and bridgmanite cannot contain the OV component
262 (**Fig. 7**). In more realistic estimations, the phases coexisting with bridgmanite in the MORB
263 compositions will not be stishovite + corundum but stishovite + NAL-phase. Nevertheless,
264 bridgmanite in the MORB compositions will virtually contain no OV component.

265 The OV component in bridgmanite may transport some volatiles such as water ([Navrotsky,](#)
266 [1999](#); [Murakami *et al.*, 2002](#)) and noble gases ([Shcheka and Keppeler, 2012](#)) into the lower
267 mantle. If this assumption is correct, the present OV content in a pyrolite composition leads to
268 a maximum water content of 1 wt% and significant noble gases such as argon and krypton
269 above 1 wt% in bridgmanite in the ambient mantle. This is enough to explain the current
270 experimental results of 1000 to 2000 ppm of water incorporation in Al-bearing bridgmanite in
271 a peridotite composition ([Murakami *et al.*, 2002](#); [Litasov *et al.*, 2003](#)). However,
272 [Bolfan-Casanova *et al.* \(2001\) and \(2003\)](#), [Litasov *et al.* \(2003\)](#), and [Panero *et al.* \(2015\)](#)
273 reported that Al-Fe-bearing bridgmanite could contain very limited amounts of water (10-400
274 ppm). These observations could be explained by the fact that Al and Fe³⁺ form the FeAlO₃
275 component in bridgmanite, which may diminish the OV component. Bridgmanite in the

276 MORB composition does not incorporate water as evidenced by [Litasov et al. \(2003\)](#) and
277 volatiles because of no OV component. Thus, subducted MORB slabs will transport water and
278 noble gases into the deep lower mantle by other hydrous phase such as aluminous stishovite
279 (*e.g.*, [Pawley et al., 1993](#); [Panero et al., 2003](#)) and phase D ([Pamato et al., 2015](#)). The effects
280 of iron on the substitution mechanisms of trivalent cation in bridgmanite must be studied in
281 detail to understand the geochemical circulation between the surface and the deep mantle.

282 **4.3 Implications for slab stagnation in the lower mantle**

283 Seismic tomography studies have observed some stagnant slabs at 600–1000 km
284 depths in the lower mantle (*e.g.*, [Fukao and Obayashi, 2013](#)). Since bridgmanite is the major
285 mineral in this region, its rheological properties can thus help understand these seismically
286 observed slab stagnations (*e.g.*, [Girard et al., 2015](#)). The decreasing of OV will slow down
287 the oxygen diffusivity in bridgmanite and thus cause an increase of its viscosity. The MORB
288 slab, one of the most the most straightforward candidates, is thus more viscous than pyrolite
289 in the lower mantle because the OV in bridgmanite in the former is significantly lower than
290 the latter. More recently, a geodynamic model by [Ballmer et al. \(2017\)](#) found that bridgmanite
291 in low-Mg/Si domains would enhance viscous entrainment in the lower mantle compared with
292 high-Mg/Si regions, which may explain some stagnant slabs at ~1000 km depth. Our results
293 demonstrated here indicate that bridgmanite in low-Mg/Si domains would have a higher
294 viscosity than that in high-Mg/Si region due to an increase of the OV in bridgmanite with
295 Mg/Si ratios, providing more evidences for their results. Therefore, the chemistry defect of
296 bridgmanite with Mg/Si ratios may offer a simply explanation for some stagnant slabs in the
297 lower mantle.

298 **5. Conclusions**

299 We studied the effect of Mg/Si ratios of the bulk compositions on the $\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}$ (OV) and
300 AlAlO_3 (CC) content in bridgmanite in the ternary system $\text{MgO}-\text{AlO}_{1.5}-\text{SiO}_2$ at a pressure of

301 27 GPa and temperature of 2000 K. The OV content in bridgmanite, especially for a pyrolitic
302 Al content, significantly decreases from 5 mol% to below zero with decreasing Mg/Si ratios
303 from 1.05 to 0.99, while the CC content increases. The ternary phase relations suggest that
304 periclase would maximize the OV component in bridgmanite, while stishovite would
305 minimize this component and favor the CC component. The pyrolitic or peridotitic lower
306 mantle is located in the region of bridgmanite + periclasle or bridgmanite + periclase + CF
307 phase and thereby have significant OV components in bridgmanite. In contrast, the MORB
308 composition located in the region of bridgmanite + stishovite + corundum will contain virtually
309 no OV in bridgmanite.

310 The presence of the OV component would cause a higher molar volume than that of the CC
311 component for bridgmanite. The variation of the OV and CC components in bridgmanite with
312 bulk Mg/Si ratios thus may explain the low and high value of the bulk modulus for
313 bridgmanite under MgO-rich and SiO₂-rich conditions, respectively, in previous studies.

314 The uppermost region of the ambient lower mantle may be a chemical reservoir of volatiles
315 such as water and argon due to the significant amounts of OV in bridgmanite. However, the
316 presence of Fe, for which bridgmanite favors the FeAlO₃ component, may decrease the OV
317 component and reduce these volatiles storages. These volatile components cannot be
318 transported into the basaltic slabs by bridgmanite in the lower mantle due to a negligible
319 amount of oxygen vacancies in low Mg/Si regions. The chemistry defect of bridgmanite with
320 Mg/Si ratios may thus help explain some stagnant slabs in the lower mantle.

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429 **Fig. 1.** Starting compositions in the system MgO–AlO_{1.5}–SiO₂ (mol%) used in this study. Red circles of A and B
 430 represent starting compositions along the system MgSiO₃ (En) –MgAlO_{2.5} (Brm); yellow symbols of C and D
 431 represent those along the system MgSiO₃– MgAl₂O₄ (Sp); blue symbols of E and F represent those along the
 432 system MgSiO₃– AlO_{1.5} (Cor), purple symbols of G and H represent those along the system MgSiO₃–Al₂SiO₅
 433 (Ky). Abbreviation: En: MgSiO₃ enstatite, Brm: MgAlO_{2.5} brownmillerite, Sp: MgAl₂O₄ spinel, Cor: Al₂O₃
 434 corundum, Ky: Al₂SiO₅ kyanite.

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Fig. 2. XRD profiles of run products from various starting materials. The number in parenthesis represents miller indices of the first appearing phase. Abbreviations: Brg, bridgmanite; Cor, corundum; CF, calcium ferrite-type structure of $MgAl_2O_4$; Sti, stishovite; Per. pericalse.

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444 **Fig. 3.** BSE images of run products from various starting materials. Abbreviations: Brg, bridgmanite; Cor,
 445 corundum; CF, calcium ferrite-type structure of $MgAl_2O_4$; Per, Pericalse; Sti, stishovite; Pt, platinum.

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Fig. 4. Plots of the OV and CC components in bridgmanite with (a) Al pfu = 0.1 and (b) Al pfu > 0.1 as a function of their Mg/Si ratio. Red and blue dashed lines represent the variation of the OV and CC component, respectively. The red dotted line represents zero value of the OV content.

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Fig. 5. (a) Molar volume of bridgmanite with Al pfu of 0.1 versus Mg/Si ratios. (b) Molar volume of bridgmanite versus the MgAlO_{2.5} (OV) / AlAlO₃ (CC) content. Red and blue lines in (b), respectively, represent the linear fitting of the data in the systems MgSiO₃-MgAlO_{2.5} and MgSiO₃-Al₂O₃ in the present study. Black symbols are from Liu et al. (2017b). The red and blue digital data in (b), respectively, are the slope of molar volume versus the OV and CC component and the number in parenthesis represents the error for the last digit.

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Fig. 6. (a) Ternary phase relations in the system $\text{MgO}-\text{AlO}_{1.5}-\text{SiO}_2$ (mol%) at 27 GPa and 2000 K. (b) The magnified ternary phase relations from (a) marked by the dashed lines. Open symbols represent the starting compositions of B, D, F, and H, while solid circles are the compositions of the corresponding phases. Square solid symbols are the single bridgmanite phase synthesized from A, C, E, and G starting compositions. Abbreviations: Brg, bridgmanite; Cor, corundum; Per, periclase; CF, calcium ferrite-type structure of MgAl_2O_4 ; Sti, stishovite; CCS: charge-coupled substitution; OVS: oxygen vacancy substitution.

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Fig. 7. Phase relations in the ternary system $X^{2+}O$ ($X=Mg, Fe, Ca$ and Mn)– $Y^{3+}O_{1.5}$ ($Y=Al, Fe,$ and Cr)– SiO_2 (mol%) for the upper part of the lower mantle. The blue and purple stars, respectively, represent the compositions of the pyrolite and MORB models for the case 1 and 2. The case 1 is that $Fe^{3+}/\Sigma Fe$ in the lower mantle is identical to that (3 %) in the upper mantle. The case 2 is that the $Fe^{3+}/\Sigma Fe$ ratio of bridgmanite in equilibrium with metallic Fe is more than 50% for a typical mantle Al_2O_3 content. Abbreviations: Brg, bridgmanite; Cor, corundum; Per, periclase; CF, calcium ferrite-type structure of $MgAl_2O_4$; Sti, stishovite.

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490 **Table 1.** Starting materials, experimental conditions, and runs products

Let.	Start Comp.	Run No.	P (27 GPa) / T (2000 K) / t (hours)	Phases
A	En ₉₀ Brm ₁₀	IRIS423	5	Brg
B	En ₅₂ Brm ₄₈	IRIS427	22	Brg + CF phase + Per
B*	En ₅₂ Brm ₄₈ *	IRIS478 [#]	20	Brg + CF phase + Per
C	En ₉₅ Sp ₅	IRIS450	6	Brg
D	En ₅₀ Sp ₅₀	IRIS446	26	Brg + CF phase + Cor
D*	En ₅₀ Sp ₅₀ *	IRIS478 [#]	20	Brg + CF phase + Cor
E	En ₉₅ Cor ₅	IRIS423	Same with A	Brg
F	En ₅₀ Cor ₅₀	IRIS427	Same with B	Brg + Cor
G	En ₉₅ Ky ₅	IRIS450	Same with C	Brg + Sti
H	En ₅₀ Ky ₅₀	IRIS446	Same with D	Brg + Sti + Cor

491 Abbreviations: Brg, bridgmanite; CF phase, calcium ferrite-type structure of MgAl₂O₄; Per, periclase; Cor,
 492 corundum; Sti, stishovite;

493 *presents the starting material for B and D synthesized under 27 GPa and 2000 K for 22 hours;

494 # represents the reversed experiment.

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496 **Table 2.** Chemical compositions of the synthesized bridgmanite.

Let.	Phases	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Total	Mg	Al	Si	O	Mg/Si	OV (mol.%)	CC (mol.%)
A	Brg (n = 18)	39.17 (43)	5.12 (33)	55.47 (77)	99.77 (76)	0.974 (7)	0.100 (7)	0.926 (6)	2.976 (4)	1.05 (2)	4.9 (13)	2.6 (3)
C	Brg (n = 48)	39.21 (48)	5.04 (19)	57.21 (75)	101.46 (92)	0.962 (9)	0.098 (4)	0.941 (5)	2.990 (5)	1.02 (2)	2.1 (13)	3.8 (4)
E	Brg (n = 26)	37.93 (22)	5.11 (12)	56.31 (30)	99.35 (55)	0.952 (5)	0.101 (2)	0.948 (4)	2.998 (3)	1.00 (1)	0.4 (8)	4.9 (3)
G	Brg (n = 30)	38.43 (55)	5.09 (18)	57.87 (55)	101.39 (66)	0.945 (10)	0.099 (4)	0.955 (6)	3.005 (6)	0.99 (2)	-1.0 (15)	5.5 (8)
B	Brg (n = 15)	37.34 (51)	8.09 (36)	54.48 (56)	99.90 (88)	0.930 (8)	0.159 (6)	0.910 (5)	2.989 (5)	1.02 (2)	2.0 (13)	7.0 (4)
B*	Brg (n = 25)	37.76 (53)	8.31 (35)	54.79 (46)	100.87(75)	0.931 (9)	0.162 (6)	0.906 (7)	2.988 (5)	1.03 (2)	2.5 (15)	6.9 (8)
D	Brg (n = 23)	37.00 (46)	10.52 (31)	54.39 (49)	101.92 (69)	0.904 (7)	0.203 (6)	0.891 (4)	2.992 (5)	1.02 (1)	1.3 (8)	9.5 (6)
D*	Brg (n = 16)	36.53 (44)	10.95 (42)	53.83 (61)	101.18 (89)	0.899 (6)	0.213 (8)	0.889 (7)	2.995 (4)	1.01 (1)	1.0 (10)	10.1 (5)
F	Brg (n = 15)	35.50 (52)	12.56 (31)	52.77 (32)	101.02 (98)	0.878 (7)	0.246 (6)	0.876 (4)	2.999 (5)	1.00 (1)	0.2 (9)	12.2 (7)
H	Brg (n = 14)	36.58 (48)	10.85 (53)	54.72 (37)	102.15 (60)	0.893 (10)	0.209 (9)	0.896 (6)	3.000 (5)	1.00 (2)	0 (1)	10.6 (4)

497 Oxide analyses are reported in wt.%. n: number of analysis points. The total cation number is normalized to two. Number in parentheses
 498 represents the standard deviation for the last digit (s). Abbreviations: Brg, bridgmanite; OV, MgAlO_{2.5}; CC, AlAlO₃.

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